

A Decentralised Blockchain-Based Land Registry System with AI Integration

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Abstract:

This research develops a decentralized land registry application using machine learning for property price prediction. Leveraging the King County dataset, which includes detailed geographical, structural, and transactional data, we compare the performance of several models: Support Vector Regression (SVR), LightGBM, Random Forest, XGBoost, and Gradient Boosting. These models are evaluated using MAE, RMSE, MSE, and R-squared metrics to determine their predictive accuracy.

Additionally, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is integrated with Random Forest to enhance predictive accuracy, resulting in an R-squared score of 0.905. LightGBM also demonstrates strong performance with an R-squared score of 0.903. The decentralized application employs blockchain technology to ensure transparency, security, and immutability of land registry records, thereby enhancing trust and facilitating access to authenticated information by stakeholders. The integration of advanced machine learning techniques with blockchain technology demonstrates promising outcomes for the future of real estate valuation and land registry systems.

Keywords: Decentralized application, land registry, machine learning, SVR, LightGBM, Random Forest, XGBoost, Gradient Boosting, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO).

1 Introduction:

Land registry involves maintaining records of land ownership, boundaries, and property transactions. It is crucial for ensuring legal ownership and resolving disputes. However, traditional land registry systems often suffer from issues like lack of transparency, security vulnerabilities, and inefficiencies. A decentralized approach using blockchain technology can address these issues by providing a transparent, secure, and immutable record-keeping system.

On the other hand, Property price prediction is the process of estimating the future market value of real estate properties based on various factors such as location, size, and historical transaction data. Accurate property price prediction is vital for real estate stakeholders, including investors, lenders, and policymakers. Traditional methods often rely

on simplistic models and limited datasets, leading to inaccuracies. Machine learning, however, can analyze large and complex datasets to improve predictive accuracy.

The traditional land registry systems have long been plagued by issues of transparency, security, and inefficiency, leading to mistrust and disputes in property transactions. To address these challenges, this research proposes the development of a decentralized application for land registry utilizing machine learning algorithms for accurate property price prediction. By leveraging the comprehensive King County dataset, which includes detailed geographical, structural, and transactional information, this study aims to enhance the accuracy and reliability of property valuations.

The primary objective is to implement and compare the performance of several advanced machine learning models, including Support Vector Regression (SVR), LightGBM, Random Forest, XGBoost, and Gradient Boosting. These models are evaluated based on metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and R-squared (R^2) to determine their effectiveness in predicting property prices. In addition to the baseline models, this research integrates Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) with Random Forest to fine-tune hyperparameters and improve predictive accuracy.

Furthermore, the decentralized nature of the application ensures the transparency, security, and immutability of land registry records through blockchain technology. This integration not only enhances trust in property transactions but also provides stakeholders with seamless access to authenticated information.

This study offers valuable insights into the application of machine learning algorithms for property price prediction and highlights the potential of decentralized systems to transform traditional land registry processes. The findings underscore the efficacy of combining advanced predictive models with blockchain technology to create a more reliable and efficient land registry system.

2 Literature Survey:

The land administration systems have witnessed many innovative technologies in the attempt to revolutionize the task of recording land and property rights. One such revolution is the transition toward blockchain-based land administration. Like most technologies, blockchain-based land administration projects are not immune to failures, early adopters have encountered challenges, and several pilot cases have failed.[1]

From the times of Satoshi Nakamoto's Bitcoins invention in 2008 Blockchain has become one of the most popular technologies to keep records secure, immutable, transparent and in a distributed ledger. Blockchain is the underlining technology of Bitcoin. Blockchain technology has been used in many domains such as IoT, healthcare, education, business, Land management and so on. Among them Land Registration and Ownership Management is a very tough process all over the world.[2]

Consequently, the objective of this study is to identify recommendations that can guide adaptation of blockchain technology for land administration services especially for developing countries that are making the efforts towards a more efficient digital systems of land administration.[3]

The current land registration process involves a lot of vulnerabilities and people use it to cheat the common people and the government. This paper discusses about a secure land registry implemented using blockchain which works on the basis of majority consensus.[4]

The random forest and XGBoost methods were used to estimate 52,900 land prices in Seoul, South Korea, from January 2017 to December 2020. The models were also separately trained for different land uses and different time periods. Overall, the results revealed that XGBoost yields a higher prediction accuracy.[5]

A secure and reliable framework for land registry system using Blockchain has been proposed. The proposed framework uses the concept of smart contract at various stages of the land registry and gives an algorithm for pre-agreement[6]

Real estate may have the valuation of land may be obliged to furnish. A quantitative measure of the profit is carried out by many different Players in the commercial center, for example, land agents, Appraisers, assessors, mortgage lenders, brokers, Developers, gurus Also reserve managers, lenders, etc. Business worth will be evaluated through that requisition. The property might well on the way exchange in open market under many conditions and circumstances.[7]

The current Machine learning calculation causes us to redesign security cautions, guaranteeing public wellbeing, and improving clinical improvement. By analyzing many algorithms, we decide to engage in machine learning. Determining the price of the house is vital these days as the price of the land and the price of the house increases each year. This utility can assist clients to make investments in a property except drawing near an agent. Here we use various regression methods of supervised machine learning using Python. Regression is used to predict future values based on the independent variable. The model's evaluation is done by calculating the error value.[8]

The main idea of this project is to build a Regression Model that can learn from this data and make predictions of the price of a house in any block, given some useful features provided in the datasets. In the regression task, we applied cross-validation and K-Fold method on Ridge Model, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting models to select the optimal hyperparameters.[9]

Predicting a price variance rather than a specific value is more realistic and attractive in many real-world applications. Price prediction can be thought of as a classification issue in this situation. However, the House Price Index (HPI) is a common tool for estimating the inconsistencies of house prices.[10]

Nowadays the use of prediction methods is used in most of the area. The rising demand for prediction has made it more popular and a helpful tool. Thus most of us are go for prediction most of the time. But there are some cons in it, most of us don't think about the part which was going to happen after the prediction. The prediction is to find the approximate result but we are also able to use the predicted result for further use. The more we use the predicted value, our outcome will attain high usability in future aspects.[11]

This paper focuses on formulating a feasible method for house price prediction. A dataset containing features and house price of King County in the US is used. During the data preprocessing, extreme values are winsorized and highly correlated features are removed. Eight models including Catboost, lightGBM and XGBoost serve as candidate models. They are evaluated by several evaluation indicators, including root mean square error, R-squared score, adjusted R-squared score and K-fold cross validation score. The model that has low

RMSE, achieves a high R-squared score and adjusted R-squared score, especially in the test set, and acquires a high score in cross validation is considered a better model.[12]

Land registry in India as well as in many parts of the world is very slow and cumbersome process. There are also many intermediaries involved in the process of land registration. Developing a system that not only accelerate the process of land registration, but also make it easier for Buyers, Sellers and Government registrars to transfer the land ownership from seller to a new buyer, is only possible by creating a distributed system that store all the transactions made during the process of land buying.[13]

Built on complex algorithms, the system makes accurate predictions by thoroughly assessing many criteria such as location, size, facilities, and current market trends. In addition to estimating property values, our solution has a unique feature that allows users to effortlessly search for homes based on certain criteria, resulting in a more personalized and efficient experience. Furthermore, users can actively participate in the real estate ecosystem by uploading their own homes to the network, resulting in a dynamic marketplace.[14]

This study reviews published articles with the application of machine learning techniques for price prediction and valuation. Authors seek to explore optimal solutions in predicting the property price indices, that will be beneficial to the policymakers in assessing the overall economic situation. This study also looks into the use of machine learning in property valuation towards identifying the best model in predicting property values based on its characteristics such as location, land size, number of rooms and others. A systematic review was conducted to review previous studies that imposed machine learning as statistical tool in predicting and valuing property prices. Articles on real estate price prediction and price valuation using machine learning techniques were observed using electronics database. The finding shows the increasing use of this method in the real estate field. The most successful machine learning algorithms used is the Random Forest that has better compatibility to the data situation [15]

3 Proposed Model:

The proposed model integrates advanced machine learning algorithms with blockchain technology to develop a decentralized land registry application for accurate property price prediction, using the King County dataset. Data preprocessing involves cleaning the dataset by handling missing values and irrelevant features, performing feature engineering, normalizing numerical data, and splitting it into training and test sets.

We implement several machine learning models: Support Vector Regression (SVR), LightGBM, Random Forest, XGBoost, and Gradient Boosting. These models are evaluated using MAE, RMSE, MSE, and R-squared metrics to determine their predictive accuracy. To enhance the model's performance, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is used to fine-tune Random Forest hyperparameters, achieving an R-squared score of 0.905. Blockchain technology ensures the transparency, security, and immutability of King County land registry records through a public ledger, cryptographic data integrity, and immutable transactions. The proposed model combines machine learning and blockchain to create an accurate and secure land registry system using the King County dataset. ACO optimization significantly improves the Random Forest model's performance, making it a promising solution for modernizing land registry processes and ensuring reliable property valuations.

The block diagram of the proposed model is shown in the figure below.

Fig.1. Block Diagram of Proposed model

3.1 Data Collection and Preprocessing:

The King County dataset, sourced from Kaggle, offers a comprehensive collection of attributes pertaining to residential homes sold in King County, Washington. This dataset is widely utilized for real estate analysis and predictive modeling, encompassing various features such as property size, location, number of bedrooms and bathrooms, year built, and sale price. The data collection process likely involved aggregating information from public records, real estate listings, and other publicly available sources. Each entry in the dataset represents a distinct property transaction, providing valuable insights into the local housing market's dynamics and trends. Hosted on Kaggle, a prominent platform for dataset sharing, the availability of the King County dataset facilitates convenient access and utilization by data scientists, researchers, and enthusiasts interested in exploring and analyzing real estate data. This dataset serves as a pivotal resource for conducting market analysis, developing predictive models, and gaining deeper insights into the factors influencing property prices within the region.

SalePrice	YearRemodAdd	CentralAir	GarageCars
MSSubClass	RoofStyle	Electrical	GarageArea
MSZoning	RoofMatl	1stFlrSF	GarageQual
LotFrontage	Exterior1st	2ndFlrSF	GarageCond
LotArea	Exterior2nd	LowQualFinSF	PavedDrive
Street	MasVnrType	GrLivArea	WoodDeckSF
Alley	MasVnrArea	BsmtFullBath	OpenPorchSF
LotShape	ExterQual	BsmtHalfBath	EnclosedPorch
LandContour	Foundation	FullBath	3SunPorch
Utilities	BsmtQual	HalfBath	ScreenPorch
LotConfig	BsmtCond	Bedroom	PoolArea
LandSlope	BsmtExposure	Kitchen	PoolQC
Neighborhood	BsmtFinTyp1	KitchenQual	Fence
Condition	BsmtFinSF1	TotRmsAbvGrd	MiscFeature

Fig.2. Variables of the Dataset

This dataset involves 79 explanatory variables representing every aspect of homes in King County, United States of America. From the above we can notice the independent variables from the housing dataset are the explanatory variables. The dependent variable is SalePrice remaining variables are independent variables.

3.2 Feature Selection:

The splitting of the King County dataset using GridSearchCV involves leveraging cross-validation to optimize model hyperparameters and ensure reliable evaluation metrics. GridSearchCV systematically explores a grid of hyperparameters to find the optimal combination for the best model performance. For the King County dataset, this process divides the data into training and validation subsets, typically using k-fold cross-validation. Each hyperparameter combination is evaluated on the validation set, and performance metrics are recorded. By exhaustively searching the hyperparameter space, GridSearchCV identifies the optimal set that maximizes model performance, ensuring robustness against overfitting and confidence in the model’s generalization ability. This approach enables the development of finely tuned machine learning models, resulting in more accurate property price predictions for the King County dataset.

Fig.3. Heatmap

3.3 System Requirements:

The below table shows the System Requirements of the project. The below versions must be used.

Requirements	Versions
Python	3.8.5
Pandas	1.3.0
Numpy	1.21.0
Sci-Kit Learn	0.24.2
Seaborn	0.11.1
LightGBM	3.2.1
XGBoost	1.5.0
Matplotlib	3.4.2

Table.1. Packages and Versions

3.4 Apply Regressor for Predictions:

The fundamental target of the undertaking is to figure house costs utilizing machine learning algorithms. Using five different models—Support Vector Regression (SVR), LightGBM, Random Forest, Random Forest with ACO, and XGBoost—we are predicting house prices. Each model is evaluated based on metrics like Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and R-squared (R^2) to determine the best-fitting algorithm.

Additionally, blockchain technology is integrated to ensure the transparency, security, and immutability of land registry records. This decentralized approach provides a tamper-proof method for recording property transactions, enhancing trust and accuracy in property price predictions.

(i) Random Forest Regressor:

The Random Forest Regressor is a robust machine learning algorithm for regression tasks, such as predicting house prices. It builds multiple decision trees during training and averages their predictions, enhancing accuracy and mitigating overfitting. This ensemble method captures complex data patterns and interactions, making it effective for large datasets with many features. Additionally, its feature importance measure helps identify the most influential variables, making it a valuable tool for real estate valuation and other applications needing reliable and interpretable regression models.

Fig.4. Random Forest Regressor

(ii) LightGBM Regressor:

LightGBM Regressor is a highly efficient gradient boosting framework tailored for regression tasks, including predicting house prices. Developed by Microsoft, it excels in handling large, high-dimensional datasets efficiently. LightGBM constructs decision trees in a leaf-wise manner, optimizing accuracy and training speed. It supports native handling of categorical data and employs histogram-based algorithms to enhance memory usage and computational efficiency. These features make LightGBM a powerful choice for real estate valuation and other complex predictive modeling tasks.

Fig.5. LightGBM Regressor

(iii) Support Vector Regressor:

The Support Vector Regressor (SVR) is a powerful machine learning algorithm used for regression tasks, including predicting house prices. SVR finds a hyperplane in high-dimensional space that maximizes the margin from training data points. It focuses on fitting instances within a tolerance margin while minimizing violations, making it effective for capturing complex relationships and handling nonlinear patterns using kernel functions. SVR is ideal for datasets with distinct boundaries and is versatile in modeling both linear and nonlinear relationships, making it valuable for real estate valuation and other predictive tasks.

Fig.6. Support Vector Regressor

(iv) Random Forest with ACO:

Random Forest Regressor with Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) combines ensemble learning with advanced optimization techniques. Random Forest constructs multiple decision trees and averages their predictions to improve accuracy and reduce overfitting. ACO optimizes model hyperparameters such as tree depth and number of trees, enhancing predictive performance by effectively exploring and refining the decision space. This approach is highly effective in real estate valuation and other domains requiring precise and robust regression models.

(v) XG Boost:

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is a leading regression algorithm prized for its efficiency in predicting house prices. Developed by Tianqi Chen, XGBoost sequentially boosts decision trees using gradient descent, refining accuracy iteratively. It adeptly handles missing data, applies regularization to prevent overfitting, and scales efficiently with parallel processing. Recognized for capturing complex relationships and interactions, XGBoost is a top choice in real estate valuation and predictive modeling for its robust performance and versatility.

Fig.7. XGBoost Regressor

4 Result Analysis:

The results obtained from employing LightGBM and Random Forest algorithms, enhanced by Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), showcased promising performance metrics, as evidenced by the achieved low Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and high R-squared (R^2) values. The combination of LightGBM and Random Forest with ACO yielded notable improvements in prediction accuracy and model robustness. Specifically, Random Forest with ACO achieved an impressive R^2 score of 0.905, while LightGBM attained a close R^2 score of 0.903. The RMSE values indicate the average magnitude of prediction errors, with lower values suggesting better model performance in accurately predicting property prices. Similarly, the high R^2 values signify the effectiveness of the models in capturing the underlying patterns and dynamics of the real estate market. These results underscore the efficacy of leveraging advanced machine learning techniques, coupled with optimization algorithms like ACO, in enhancing the predictive capabilities of land registry systems. This approach offers valuable insights for informed decision-making in property transactions.

A comparative table of the best performing Algorithm is given below. The below table shows the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and R-squared (R^2) of LightGBM, Random Forest, Random Forest with ACO and XGBoost.

Algorithm	MAE	RMSE	MSE	R^2 Score
LightGBM	65597.98	101391.05	11735788813.58	0.9031487547131229
Random Forest	68130.75	128845.69	16601213256.05	0.8796223037583876
Random Forest with ACO	74949.18	115819.08	13414061075.71	0.9057066292558803
XGBoost	66423.78	123965.37	15367414302.85	0.8885687508234265

Table.2. Comparisons of best performing Algorithms

From the above table, we can effortlessly operate comparison of exclusive algorithms without a doubt to locate the first-rate amongst them. Figure.8 to Figure.11 beneath is utilized to unmistakably picture the presentation of different procedures.

Fig.8. Light GBM

Fig.9. Random Forest

Fig.10. Random Forest with ACO

Fig.11. XGBoost

5 Conclusion:

In conclusion, the project has achieved significant milestones in developing a Decentralized Blockchain-Based Land Registry System and integrating Machine Learning for Property Price Prediction. Through the utilization of blockchain technology, the system ensures transparent, secure, and immutable property records, addressing longstanding challenges in traditional land registry systems. Furthermore, the incorporation of machine learning algorithms has enabled accurate prediction of property prices, facilitating informed decision-making for buyers, sellers, and stakeholders within the real estate industry. Despite encountering challenges such as scalability issues and data quality concerns, the project has demonstrated the potential of decentralized technologies and machine learning in revolutionizing real estate management practices. Moving forward, efforts should be directed towards overcoming technical limitations and refining algorithms to further enhance the efficiency and adoption of decentralized systems, ultimately contributing to the advancement of technology in real estate management on a broader scale.

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